

Entomophagy and Possible Transmission Risk Indices of Edible Termites (Isoptera: Termitidae) in Rural Areas of Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The first report on entomophagy, consumption of insects (including termites) as food and possible transmission risk of infections to humans based on study conducted in June 2018 and 2019 is reported. Samples of soil in/around edible termites hide outs and winged reproductive termites, *Macrotermis* species locally called “aku ebe” were collected and examined for helminth ova towards highlighting the public health significance. Of the 120 soil and 445 termites examined using ZnSo₄ centrifuged floatation and filtration techniques, 18.5% and 20.0% were positive respectively. Ova of *Ascaris lumbricoides* (10.0%), Hookworm (1.67%), *Toxocara* species (3.33%) and cyst of *Entamoeba histolytica* (4.17%) were recovered from the soil while cyst/ova found on termites were *Ascaris* (7.64%), *Toxocara* (1.79%), Hookworm (2.69%) and *E. histolytica* (1.12%) respectively. There was a significant relationship between sampling sites and termites parasite carriage ($r=0.86$; $P<0.05$). The prevalence of ova/cysts in the soil and on termites was not influenced by the sites ($P>0.05$). Termites’ pathogen carriage could be attributable to indiscriminate disposal of faeces in the study area and suggested that the risk of spreading infections may be enhanced by consumption. While the risk indices were assessed, intervention by means of education (on poor hygiene status and danger of consuming raw or improperly prepared termites) and legislation against indiscriminate disposal of faeces as well as its enforcement is recommended.

Keywords: Entomophagy, Edible Termites, helminthes carriage, Risk indices

Introduction

Insects are man’s chief competitor as well as his benefactor on earth. Majority of them are harmful and serve as vectors of human and animal disease. The endemic occurrence of high level of some insect borne disease has greatly retarded social and economic development in several

developing countries. Conversely, some are useful. For instance, Silk and honey / bee wax are produced from the salivary gland of *Bombyx mori* (Saturnid moth) and the *Apis mellifera* (Honey bee), *Dactylopius locus* is a major source of the brilliant red dye while commercial shellac from *Keuria lacca* (Lac insect) is widely eaten in USA, India, Thailand and other Asian countries. Insects also play role in pollination of flowers and act as scavengers by biodegradation of dead trees. Recently, a technique for treatment of osteomyelitis using blowfly larvae (Calliphoridae) was developed (Service, 1980). The maggots digest the surface tissue of the wound, engulf and feed on the micro-organisms, hence making the drugs applied to work faster (NGN, 2003).

Entomophagy (consumption of insects as food) is common culture in many parts of the world including Africa. The role played by edible insects in the nutrition, arts, customs and beliefs of indigenous people cannot be over emphasized. Termites, Crickets, caterpillars, grubs and Locusts are edible. Entomophagous insects in Nigeria are well documented (Okore et al., 2014; Ebenebe and Okpoko, 2015). This practice is not new in Nigeria (DeFoliet, 2002) were it is important source of high food protein for rural city dwellers. The larvae of *Cirina forda* (Lepidoptera: Saturnidae) and adult of *Zonocerus* species (Orthoptera: Pyrgomohidae) are consumed in parts of Nigeria (Ogunleye and Omotoso, 2005) as well as substitutes in food ratio for experimental Albino rat (Ogunleye and Edward, 2005) and fishes (Michael and Imrecsaves, 1993). Winged reproductive termites, *Macrotermis* species locally known as ‘akuebe’ are prominent among edible insects in south eastern part of Nigeria where they serve as alternative source of protein (Ebenebe and Okpoko, 2015). Previous studies on termites have either centered on pest species or checklist on entomophagy. Hitherto no study is known to have associated edible insects with carriage of pathogens. Rural areas of Imo State Nigeria are known for poor sanitary habits coupled with a high prevalence of parasite infections (Ogomaka et al., 2012; Odinaka et al., 2015; Iwunze et al., 2017). Termites are known to swarm (or undergo nuptial flight) during the onset of rainy season.

The latter pair in groups (in search for mates and sites) after losing their wings and both soil and other materials are utilized for cover/ shelter. Termites harvested from these places (locally called ‘ivo aku’) are often eaten raw or spiced on food by consumers. This served as hypothesis for the present work. The desire to study aspect of pathogen carriage of edible insects and x-ray

their epidemiological implications excited this study in selected rural areas of Imo state South East, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Areas

The study areas included ten rural villages in Obowo Local Government Area of Imo State, Nigeria. The study areas have been described in details (Iwunze and Amaechi 2025; Iwunze et al 2024; Iwunze, 2024,2023).

Collection of Samples

This included both termites and soil samples where termites were collected. Winged reproductive edible termites, 30-40 individuals were collected from sample units in the morning (6:00-10:00am) usually after nuptial flight in the night. These units/sources were chosen to reflect places where children rummage and preferred; (schools, around house/buildings, markets and roads leading to home and schools). Termites picked with hand gloves and entomological forceps were emptied into sample bottles, labeled and taken to the laboratory within 3-4 hours for identification and analysis. Notes were taken on circumstances associated with termites collected. One hundred and twenty (120) soil samples were collected from the sampling units where termites were collected (table 2). About 20g of top soil (down to a depth of not more than 2cm) was scooped into clean polythene bags using a clean garden towel and taken to the Parasitology Laboratory, Imo State University Owerri for analysis.

Identification of Termites and Parasitological Analysis

Termites caught were identified with keys of Ethiopian genera of the Macrotermitinae by Imagon and Soldiers and cross checked with already identified specimen preserved in Entomology Unit Laboratory of Imo State University Owerri, Nigeria. Thereafter the termites were immersed in normal saline and stirred with an applicator stick for 5 minutes to wash off any parasite ova or larvae. The washed termites were then removed with forceps while suspension was subjected to concentration by filtration technique. Paper filters were placed on filter holders before passage of the contents of the bottle. The residue together with the filter paper were removed with the forceps and placed on microscope slide. A drop of Lugol's iodine was added and about 10 seconds allowed for stain to penetrate. The whole filters were examined under the

microscope at low power (x40). The cysts /ova were identified with reference to Cheesbrough (1992). Termites were not dissected for gut parasites examination because wandering activities (apetentive or epigamic behaviour) is for mate and site selection rather than feeding.

Examination of Soil Samples

5g of each sample was placed in a polythene tube and distilled water added. The soil was broken up and mixed with water using a glass rod. The tube was covered and shaken for one minute (Dada and Linqvist, 1979). The suspension was then strained through wet cheese cloth placed over funnel, to remove coarse particles. The tube was refilled with water and the suspension centrifuged again. The suspension was decanted and the process repeated until the supernatant was clear. This was decanted and enough ZnSO₄ solution (specific gravity of 1.2) added to the brim of the tube. A cover slip placed over the top of the tube and allowed to stand for 3 minutes (Neva and Brown, 1994). Parasites ova were identified by reference to atlases of Parasitology (Cheesbough, 1992). Identification of *Toxocara* species was based on recognition of specific morphological characteristics (Soulsby, 1982).

Data Management and Analysis

The results were analysed using SPSS software (version 16.0). Comparative analysis involving two categories of variables was done using Chi Square test. The significant level of each test was set at $P < 0.05$

Results

A total of 60 (13.48%) ova / cysts of parasites were found to be carried by termites (Table 1). The pattern of distribution from wash up water on the termites revealed the presence of 3 helminths; *Ascaris lumbriciodes* (34, 7.64%), Hookworm (12, 2.69%), and *Toxocara* species (8, 1.38%) and a protozoa, *E. histolytica* (6, 1.12%). Infection rates of parasites from different sites / units are summarised (Table 2; Figure 1). There was a significant relationship between sites and parasites carriage ($r=0.86$; $P < 0.05$). Consequently, infection was significantly higher in schools (18.49%) followed by roads (13.33%) with the market (7.61%) as the least ($P > 0.05$). Hookworm and *E. histolytica* was not found in samples from markets. Of the 120 soil samples examined, 24 (20.0%) had geohelminthes ova. The distribution according to sources is shown in Table 3. The differences observed among the sites / units were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$).

Discussion

Our findings further support the notion that animals separated from their natural habitats are susceptible to infections and insects including termites are no exception. The soil samples from the study area contained ova of *Ascaris*, *Toxocara*, Hookworm and cyst of *Entamoeba* species to the level of 20.0%. The fact that the adult stages of these parasites resides in the gut is indicative of faecal pollution. Probably, this resulted from poor hygiene habits of the inhabitants mostly associated with open air defecation, socio-economic status and poor animal husbandry. While *Toxocara* species could be traced to stray dogs feaces which abound in the streets of the area, the recovery of other parasites in the soil samples supports earlier studies (Nock et al ., 2003; Nock and Duada, 2000).

The presence of these parasites ova/cyst on termites (not typical of them on their natural habitats) underscores the availability of environmental conditions that favour these parasites survival and spread. This observation together with termite status as most cherished delicacy is of public concern. Edible termites are harvested for consumption with variety of techniques involving contacts with soil. Their creeping habits and contact with contaminated soil is germane for pathogen carriage and possible transmission (survival strategy). Given that among edible insects termites are often eaten raw or spiced on food could places some individuals (especially children) at greater risk, thus a call for further inquest. Furthermore, the presence of ova on termites could facilitate their dissemination both far and wide were they serve as transport agents.

The high level of helminthes in soil and on termites (90% ova and 10% cyst) could be due to favourable edaphic and biotic factors for parasites transmission. Tropical climatic conditions have been known to favour the development and survival of parasitic nematomorphs larvae to infective stage. Also, the high level from different sources gives a vivid reflection of the poor state of hygiene in the area. The significant relationship between the sites and termites pathogen carriage is a disturbing indication that the eggs / infection have the potential to use termites as agents of transmission to humans or other animals consumed directly or indirectly by humans like amphibians, reptiles and birds. Geohelminthiasis in children is a serious health problem. For example, hookworm infection leads to decreased productivity, reduced rate of cognitive development, poor performance at school, increased absenteeism from school and susceptibility to infections (Stephenson, 1994). It is a fact that local control of geohelminthes can only be

reached if transmission agents are identified. By confirming edible termites as risk factors, our study has showcased a potential underlying cause of transmission and also provided interventions.

Conclusion and Recommendations.

Conclusively, edible termites found to be contaminated with helminth pathogens could indicate that humans are always at risk of infection especially as termites are used as delicacy (raw or improperly prepared) in the diet of all classes of inhabitants. For termites and edible insects, no knowledge on pathogen carriage exist and lesson learned from these should be implemented for control of diseases in/on edible insect population. Therefore, adequate preventive measures like proper roasting and deep frying of the termites should be adopted by the people who consumed them as a special food as part of prophylactic and pre-control measures against upsurge of helminth parasites infection in the area. Also, there is need for public health promotion to be stepped up on emerging parasite carriage and transmission by termites and by extension other edible insects. Education is an important tool that can be used and house-to-house approach is a good starting point. Education on poor hygiene habits should be accompanied by legislation and its follow up enforcement towards having and sustaining a clean and intestinal parasite- free environment. Further research on edible insects needs to include basic studies on emerging insect diseases; biological, genetic characterization, host range, transmission and safety for animals including humans.

Contribution of Authors

IJI and UGM suggested and designed the project. OJC, NMC, UOP, AGE, and NGU participated in the field work and data collection. NMC and UGM performed the data analysis and interpretation. IJI prepared the first manuscript reviewed by all. All authors contributed to the development of the final manuscript and approved its submission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of the paper

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Ethics declaration

Not applicable.

References

Cheesbrough M 1992. *Medical Laboratory Manual for Tropical countries* (2nd Edition) University Press Cambridge. Pp20-357

Dada BJ and Linqvist WD 1979. Studies on the floatation techniques for recovery of helminth eggs from soil and the prevalence of eggs of *Toxocara* spp in some Kansas public places. *Journal of the American Veterinary Medicine Association*, 174:1208-1210

DeFoliert GR 2002. *The human use of insects as food resources: A bibliographic account in progress* University of Wincousin Madison

Ebenebe CI and Okpoko VO 2015. Edible insect consumption in the south eastern Nigeria. *Scientific and Engineering Research* 6 (issue 6).

Iwunze JI, Amaechi AA, Ihome JN, Njoku FU and Odemenam CC 2017. Prevalence of Intestinal Parasites among Primary School Children in Obowo L.G.A of Imo State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Environmental and Geoscience* 1: 29-33

Iwunze J.I (2023). Knowledge, attitudes and perception on prevention and control of COVID-19 in Obowo Local Government Area Imo State Nigeria. *International Journal of Biology Sciences* 5(1): 95-98

Iwunze JI (2024): Prevalence of malaria among infants 0-5 years in a Rural Community South Eastern. *International Invention of Scientific Journal Nigeria* 8 (1)30-34

Iwunze JI, Amaechi AA, Nwoke MC, Ezike MN and Egbe, UC (2024): Malaria prevalence and preventive measures among pregnant women in Obowo L.G.A Imo State, Nigeria. *International Invention of Scientific Journal* 8 (1) 25-29

Iwunze JI and Amaechi AA (2025): Assessment of usage and challenges of Insecticide treated bed net in the control of Malaria in Obowo Local Government Area Imo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Experimental Sciences* 16: 13-17

Neva FA and Brown HW 1994. *Basic Clinical Parasitology* (6th Edition) .Prentice Hall international inc. USA, 356pp

NGN 2003. *Medicinal maggots treat as they eat*. National Geographic News, October 24, 2003

Nock IH , Duniya D and Galadinma M 2003. Geohelminth egg in the siol and stool of pupils of some primary schools in Samaru, Zaria Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology* 24: 115-122

Nock IH and Dauda T 2000. Prevalence and public health significance of parasite oocyst and ova on the sole of shoes : a case study of Zaria Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology* 21: 137-142

Odinaka KK, Nwolisa EC, Mbanefo F, Iheakaram ACand Okolo S 2015. Prevalence and pattern of soil transmitted helminthic infection among primary school children in a rural community in Imo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Tropical Medicine* 10.1155/349439

Ogunleye RF and Omotoso CT 2005. Edible orthopteran and lepidopteran as protein substitute in the feeding of Experimental Albino Rats. *African Journal of Zoology and Environmental Biology* 7:48-51

Ogunleye RF and Edward JB 2005. Roasted maggots (Diptera larvae) as a dietary protein source for laboratory animals. *African Journal of Zoology and Enviromental Biology* 7: 140-143

Ogomaka IO, Nwoke BEB, Ukaga CN, Nwokeji CM, Ajero CMU and Nwachukwu MI 2012. Prevalence of soil transmitted helminth among primary school pupils in Owerri West LGA, Imo State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology* 33(1): 37-43

Okore O, Aვაოja D and Nwanu I 2014. Edible insects of Niger Delta area in Nigeria. *Journal of Natural Science Research* 4 (5):www.ijste.org

Service MW 1980. *A guild to Medical Entomology, MacMillian Tropical and subtropical Medical Text*. MacMillian Press, London

Soulsby EJ 1982. *Helminths, Arthropods and Protozoans of domesticated animals Bailliens*, Tindal and Cassel, London(2nd Edition) 82pp

Stephenson LS 1994. Helminth Parasites a major factor in malnutrition, *World Health Organisation Forum* 15:169-172

Table 1: Infection rates of parasites recovered from Edible termites

Parasite cyst/ova recovered	School (N = 146)	Market (N = 92)	Road (N = 60)	Buildings (N = 147)	Total No (%) infection
<i>A.lumbricoides</i>	16(10.96)	06(6.52)	03(5.00)	09(6.12)	34(7.64)
Hookworm	06(4.11)	00(0.00)	03(5.00)	03(2.00)	12(2.69)
<i>Toxocara species</i>	02(1.79)	01(1.09)	01(1.67)	04(2.72)	08(1.79)
<i>E.histolytica</i>	03(2.05)	0(0.00)	01(1.67)	02(1.36)	06(1.12)
Total	27(18.49)	07(7.61)	08(13.33)	18(12.24)	60(13.48)

Table 2: Distribution of parasites recovered from Edible termites

Parasite	Ova	Cyst	Larvae
<i>A.lumbricoides</i>	34(7.64)	00(0.00)	00(0.00)
Hookworm	12(2.69)	00(0.00)	00(0.00)
<i>Toxocara species</i>	08(1.79)	00(0.00)	00(0.00)
<i>E.histolytica</i>	00(0.00)	06(1.12)	00(0.00)
Total	54(90.0)	06(10.00)	00(0.00)

Table 3: Prevalence of intestinal parasites recovered from soil samples around edible termites.

Sources	No of Samples	No (%) Positive	AL	HW	TS	EH
School	30	13(43.33)	07(23.33)	01(3.33)	02(6.67)	03(10.00)
Market	30	07(23.33)	02(6.67)	01(3.33)	01(3.33)	02(6.67)
Road	30	04(13.33)	03(10.00)	0(0.00)	01(3.33)	00(0.00)
Buildings	30	00(0.00)	00(0.00)	0(0.00)	00(0.00)	00(0.00)
Total	120	24(20.00)	12(10.00)	02(1.67)	04(3.33)	05(4.17)

Key:

AL	=	<i>A.lumbricoides</i>
HW	=	Hookworm
TS	=	<i>Toxocara species</i>
EH	=	<i>E.histolytica</i>

Figure 1: Phenology of intestinal parasites on edible termites from the study sites